

3D Facebook Connecting peoples

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Abstract

This study highlights the multiple roles of identification in a Facebook context. We differentiate and monitor the impacts of three key targets of identification, specifically, the identification with: a brand's Facebook page, other users of this Facebook brand page, and identification at the conventional consumer-brand level. In this study, the relevance of each target was investigated with its impact on the level of loyalty to a Facebook brand page and word-of-mouth in favor of this page. Complementary to the fancy applications of social networks, influence analysis is an indispensable technique supporting these practical applications. In recent years, this emerging research branch has obtained significant attention from both industry and

academia. In this new territory, researchers are facing many unprecedented theoretical and practical challenges. Thus, in this survey, we aim to pave a comprehensive and solid starting ground for interested readers by soliciting the latest work in this area. Firstly, we provide an overview of social networks, including definition, and types of social networks. Secondly, we present the current understanding of social influence analysis from different levels, such as its definition, properties, architecture, applications, and diffusion models. Thirdly, we discuss the evaluation metrics for social influence. Fourthly, we summarize the existing evaluation models on social influence in social networks. The innovative social networking services (SNS) provide people with versatile personal, commerce, and social applications. This study compares Facebook and LinkedIn to better understand factors affecting users' trust on SNS. Subject domain experts were invited to participate in qualitative research based interviews. Using the refined research model a quantitative empirical study was designed and conducted to investigate the relationships between important constructs including effort expectancy, social influence, privacy concern, perceived risk, trust, and continuance intention. Users' trust on SNS is mainly influenced by effort expectancy, social influence, and perceived risk.

1. Introduction

The recent years online social network site has become increasingly popular with increased revolution in how people interact with each other through the internet. (Erlin, Fitri, & Susandri, 2015) Many have debated the utility of social media for delivering suitable marketing strategy (e.g., Gao & Feng, 2016; Hutton & Fosdick, 2011; Laroche, Habibi, & Richard, 2013). 2.13 billion monthly active users of Facebook, the world's biggest social media website (Facebook, 2018), illustrate the crucial relevance of social media for companies and their brands. In recent years, social networking services (SNS)

have become a global phenomenon, attracting a great amount of people who want to share their current feelings and opinions. SNS allow users to create information content to publish on blogs, social networking sites, and online-sharing platforms. The social networking site user could be an information creator, commenter, or reviewer in a social community. Social networks (SNS), such as WeChat, Facebook, and Twitter, have emerged and tightly connected web users all over the world. By analyzing and mining social networks, we can gather information on the comments people make with respect to a particular product. Analysis of such comments shows its value for the design of marketing and advertising campaigns.

A Vehicular Social Network (VSN) is a mobile communication system formed by the combination of relevant concepts and features from the vehicular ad-hoc networks (VANETs) and social networks [1]. Network entities share data and communicate with each other exploiting the social interdependencies. The inheritance of social features and study of the vehicular system under social perspective have significant potential to improve reliability and efficiency in the vehicular environment. Different from other socially-aware networks, network entities in the VSNs are heterogeneous, including On-Body Units (OBUs), Road Side Units (RSUs), drivers', passengers' and pedestrians' smart devices. Our major contributions are:

- We present an overview of VSNs under social perspective and present a literature review of socially-aware applications for VSNs.
- We survey recent approaches to enhance data dissemination in VSNs and present a comparison of these methods.
- We focus on mobility modeling of VSNs and present a literature review of different approaches based on crowdsourcing and cloud computing to enhance urban life.
- We highlight several open research issues and future research directions.

2. Literature Review

Since Facebook has become an extraordinary phenomenon that is in today's digital society has motivated several researchers to study some effects that have been caused by this social networking. These researchers analyze based on the multiple perspectives and different points in accordance with the interests and the concentration of each researcher. This study has been reviewed several previous research. Although this review is not exhaustive, considering the limited resources and time, but could represent a review that conducted on several sources.

2.1. Facebook use for news and discussion network heterogeneity SNS

SNS users not only retain pre-existing social ties but also make new relationships with others who have a broad range of political and socioeconomic backgrounds beyond a geographical location (Ellison et al., 2007). Specifically, 53% of Facebook users and 39% of Twitter users reported that they have online friends with a mix of political views (Pew Research Center, 2016). Furthermore, many SNS users do not block or defriend their online friends just because of political disagreement (Pew Research Center, 2012).

2.2. Social network advertising effect through a semiotic perspective

The semiotic triangle provides researchers with a means of thinking about the relationship among a sign, a thought and a

reference. A sign can be defined as the word that calls up the referent through the mental processes. A thought can be defined as the realm of memories of past experiences and scenes. A referent can be defined as an object, which can be perceived as an impression in the field of thought (Ogden and Richards, 1989). More simply, the semiotic triangle can be explained in the sense that a sign uses X to represent Y to convey a certain meaning. Though X is not Y itself, it still can convey certain meaning, for it can be used to represent Y.

2.3 Significance of Conducting Feasibility Study (Teresa Luckey, Joseph Phillips, 2006)

Feasibility study being a vital phase of software projects development assists in saving time, money and identifying the risk factors. Business Consultant or Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) are considered for performing the feasibility study. The study ensures the objectivity, project requirement investigation, risk factors, cost estimates as well as the factors leading towards the software project failures and success during the project development. Conducting the feasibility study provides the motivation to the team to complete the project. Feasibility study requires certain models for estimation. One of the cost models is Constructive Cost Model (COCOMO) which is obsolete now because its accuracy is limited. So COCOMO II introduced in 1995 replaced the COCOMO. Risk mitigation strategies must also need to be reviewed during this study to ensure that the decision taken for project is acceptable.

3. METHODOLOGY

A long selection process has been carried out in order to relevant research on Facebook: after identify the most ensuring that the content was related to Facebook, the studies have been regrouped into eight main research themes: effects on the users, friendship – that is how Facebook changes the conception of friendship online, construction of impressions, information revelation and internet privacy, Facebook use,

Facebook and politics, self-expression and construal – i.e. how individuals build an image of themselves on the social network, social capital – how it is changing through Facebook, and the merging of social spheres. Then, the importance of each article has been attributed based on the number of times it had been cited by the other studies, and the year of its publication. Finally, we have removed the studies that had not been cited at all or that did not represent an academic institution. Therefore, the literature employed in this study is composed mainly of published papers or studies presented at academic conventions.

Feasibility Study Tasks	Detailed Activity	Weeks Required
Data gathering	Conduct interviews	3
	Administer questionnaires	4
	Read company reports	4
	Introduce prototype	5
	Observe reactions to prototype	3
Data flow and decision analysis	Analyze data flow	8
Proposal preparation	Perform cost/benefit analysis	3
	Prepare proposal	2
	Present proposal	2

Figure : Schedule of Feasibility Study

4. Software Testing

Software testing is the process of evaluation a software item to detect differences between given input and expected output. Also to assess the feature of A software item. Testing assesses the quality of the product. Software testing is a process that should be done during the development process. In other words software testing is a verification and validation process.

4.1 Blackbox Testing

Black box testing is a testing technique that ignores the internal mechanism of the system and focuses on the output generated against any input and execution of the system. It is also called functional testing.

4.2 Whitebox Testing

White box testing is a testing technique that takes into account the internal mechanism of a system. It is also called structural testing and glass box testing.

Black box testing is often used for validation and white box testing is often used for verification.

Figure : Test Vee Model

5. Conclusion:

The rational and expected sequitur response to the theoretical framework proposed here is to examine the intersectionality and impressions between the numerous social actors and forces. With consideration given to the cyborging of the mind and the permanently beta ideologies operating in the minds of the internet generation participants in CMC and SNS systems, we can unearth the applications to social capital, personal, cultural, and social identity, social movements, and even education. There is no simply way to determine if Facebook is good or bad, but there have been some great points that have been brought up on the topic. Social media is a serious issue in todays society, but its our choice at the end of the day as to whether or not we connect to Facebook. Perhaps Facebook should come with a warning of 'Connect at your own risk'. Some have argued that we need to get a real life and disconnect from social media and then some say we should embrace social media because without it we would fail.

In my opinion, I think we should embrace the good, the bad and even the ugly side of Facebook and just realise its apart of society.

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